

A systemic approach to networking innovation clusters in the European Construction and Built Environment R&I ecosystem

A. Zarli & A. Yurchyshyna

ECTP – European Construction Technology Platform, Brussels, Belgium

K. Laffont-Eloire & C. Coujard

DOWEL Innovation, Valbonne, France

ABSTRACT: As a key implementation instrument for achieving low carbon economy goals for 2050 by decarbonising the EU built environment, the co-programmed Built4People (B4P) Partnership was launched in 2021. It aims to support and promote the development of holistic research and innovation for an effective transition of the construction sector to sustainability. To ensure such expected sustainable and user-centred development of the Built Environment and to support the Partnership in its performance objectives, the NEBULA project was launched in October 2022, with the aim to connect to and network with a set of national or regional Innovation Clusters in Europe. The aim of this paper is to introduce the conceptual foundations for developing the network of B4P Innovation Clusters (the B4PIC network). Starting by the review of the concept of the Innovation Cluster, it introduces the notion of the B4P Innovation Cluster and proposes an evaluation framework to assess the maturity of such B4P Innovation Clusters according to a set of parameters, identified as success factors for the deployment and outreach of clusters. This conceptual framework is formalised into a maturity process for clusters, including the development of the B4PIC Charter signed by each B4PIC, that evaluates its current maturity and sets some maturity improvement targets. The approach was tested through a first call for Expression of Interest during autumn 2023, the outcome of which enabled to design a more formal application and selection process for candidate Innovation Clusters. The paper concludes on the current state of this evaluation and selection process, with a summary of future works and prospective activities aiming to support and nurture the network of B4P Innovation Clusters both during and beyond the NEBULA project.

1 INTRODUCTION

The European ambition to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 is embodied into some key policies and initiatives, including the European Green Deal (European Green Deal 2019) and its recently adopted revised ‘Fit for 55 Package’ (Fit for 55 2023). This has been also supported by research on strategic actions for R&I in construction (Kasi & al 2015).

As a key implementation instrument for achieving low carbon economy goals for 2050 by decarbonising the EU built environment, the Built4People (B4P) Partnership¹ (<http://www.built4people.eu>) was launched in 2021. The B4P Partnership is a co-programmed partnership, jointly managed by (on the public side) the European Commission and (on the private side) stakeholders’ representatives, ECTP² (European Construction and sustainable built envi-

ronment Technology Platform) and WGBC ERN³ (World Green Building Council – European Regional Network). The B4P Partnership aims to support the development of holistic research and innovation for an effective transition of the construction sector to sustainability. It brings together all players across the value chain and throughout a comprehensive building life cycle approach, so as to overcome the fragmentation of the sector and initiate a holistic transformation of the Built Environment.

In line with the New European Bauhaus (NEB 2021) which aims to bring the European Green Deal to life in an attractive, and innovative and human-centred way, the Built Environment should go beyond improving energy and resource efficiency, to include a qualitative, aesthetic and human dimension, with new creative design and architectural solutions that are essential to ensure the sustainable

¹ <http://www.built4people.eu>

² <https://ectp.org>

³ <https://worldgbc.org/>

and user-centred development of the Built Environment.

To address these challenges and to support the Partnership in its operations and achievements, the NEBULA⁴ project was launched in October 2022. The overarching objective of the NEBULA project is to connect a set of national or regional Innovation Clusters in Europe into the B4P Innovation Cluster network, to leverage on the benefits of clusters for the innovation in construction (Yfanti & al, 2017). Such a network will promote and support the deployment, demonstration and market transfer of output assets in particular from the European R&I projects in regions, thereby increasing impact at local and national level.

This paper introduces the conceptual foundations for the B4PIC maturity framework enabling the development of the network of B4P Innovation Clusters (the B4PIC network).

Section 2 reviews the concept of an Innovation Cluster and discusses how such a concept can be adjusted to the specific context of the European construction ecosystems and the objectives of the B4P Partnership. It first introduces the key concepts: Innovation Cluster (IC), B4P Innovation Cluster (B4PIC), B4PIC network, B4PIC Charter and describes 6 B4PIC success factors that define the requirements which an IC has to meet to be considered as a B4PIC.

Section 3 analyses – from one side – the B4P framework defined by its three general and seven specific objectives; as well as – from the other perspective – the NEB conceptual foundations specified by its three core values and three working principles⁵. This analysis demonstrates that the elicitation process of an IC to become a B4PIC is developed in respect to and based on both B4P and NEB complementary frameworks.

Building upon the different B4P requirements, a B4PIC maturity framework is introduced in Section 4. Such framework is based on the levels of maturity, which a B4PIC has reached on each of B4PIC success factors, and identifies the main principles of B4PIC elicitation process.

In Section 5, the paper presents how this conceptual framework is implemented through the clusters' maturity process, formalised in the B4PIC Charter signed by each IC. This allows to evaluate the current maturity of an IC according to the defined B4PIC maturity framework, and sets some maturity improvement targets.

The proposed approach was tested through a first call for Expression of Interest (EoI) during autumn 2023, which is introduced in Section 6.

Finally, the paper concludes on the current state of development of this evaluation and selection process, with a summary of future works and prospective activities aiming to support and nurture the network of B4P Innovation Clusters both during and beyond the NEBULA project.

2 KEY CONCEPTS

2.1 Innovation Cluster

A brief literature review (Meng 2005, Press 2006, Engel 2022, Official Journal of the European Union 2022, Law Insider 2024) gives several definitions and a detailed analysis of Innovation Clusters. In the context of the Built Environment, an Innovation Cluster (IC) is generally seen as a local or regional socio-technical ecosystem bringing together actors of the Built Environment value chain where pools of capital, tacit knowledge, expertise and talent foster the development of new innovations, their demonstration and their market uptake.

In addition, the EC Open Innovation Strategy and Policy Group (OISPG 2015) has been presenting the Open Innovation 2.0 paradigm as an innovation model grounded in extensive networking and collaborative co-creation among all societal participants - extending well beyond conventional licensing and collaboration frameworks and aiming at the emergence and consolidation of *innovation network ecosystems*.

2.2 B4P Innovation Cluster

Compared to the above generic definition of ICs, B4P Innovation Clusters (B4PICs) are formally defined as a group of innovation-driven stakeholders ecosystems, typically formed by one or more local/regional cluster(s), that engage in a maturing process to foster EU-scale, multidisciplinary and sustainable open innovation (potentially cross-sector and cross-border) in the Built Environment, through a formal engagement towards the B4P generic and specific objectives and targets.

2.3 B4PIC success factors

The B4PIC success factors are used to evaluate the initial maturity level of ICs and how their maturity evolves along the transformation process of becoming B4PICs.

The following six B4PIC success factors (SFs) have been identified in the scope of the NEBULA project:

⁴ NEBULA - New European Bauhaus Unlocked through Built4People-endorsed Local Actions – GA 101079859

⁵ [NEB toolbox.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

- SF1: Whole value chain: integrating as many as possible different stakeholder types from the whole Built Environment innovation value chain (e.g. any entity or organization representing academia (universities), research (RTOs), industrial innovators and innovation SMEs, architects and contractors, end users’ associations, local authorities, private funders, etc.);
- SF2: Multi-objectives: targeting several B4P objectives as well as NEB principles;
- SF3: Cross-sectoral: integrating different industrial sectors, whose members might be transdisciplinary;
- SF4: Locally anchored with National and European outreach: connecting a local territory with networks at national (national clusters or meta-clusters, e.g. Construction National Technology Platforms) and European (European clusters or meta-clusters, e.g. ECTP, WGBC ERN) levels;
- SF5: Cross-border: interconnecting (physically or virtually) with clusters from other regions or Member States, establishing and promoting inter-regional activities between two clusters operating in two different local markets or economies (e.g. in the context of Euro-regions, or in two regions within the same Member State or in two different EU countries, with clearly differentiated markets and/or economies);
- SF6: Access to testbeds and demonstration spaces: integrating or connecting to test beds, pilot buildings, living labs or other facilities to demonstrate innovations and facilitate market uptake.

2.4 B4PIC Charter

The B4PIC Charter is a declaration and commitment of ICs to work together and into the network of B4PICs to fundamentally contribute to the B4P objectives and expected impacts, while at the same time leveraging on the New European Bauhaus core values and working principles.

The B4PIC Charter defines the purpose and the rationale of this movement, formalizes commitments of ICs, describes NEBULA-based activities supporting the maturity process of B4PICs and outlines the key steps and the corresponding timeline of the implementation plan. Such an implementation plan is specifically developed for each IC engaging into the maturity process towards becoming a B4PIC and joining the B4PIC network. It also describes the maturity levels of each success factor, which this IC is aiming to achieve.

2.5 B4PIC network

The B4P Innovation Cluster network (B4PIC network) is composed of the B4PICs that have formally engaged in the B4P maturing process (i.e. signed the B4PIC Charter), ensures the exchange of good practices and fosters the collaboration among B4PICs.

Figure 1. Simplified value proposition of the B4PIC network

Thus, the B4PIC network helps B4PICs to increase their coverage (geographical, sectoral, transdisciplinary) and access to testbeds, helps to share resources, practices and knowledge among members and provides general support on finding partnership and financing opportunities. Such a network is instrumental to boost innovation and reduce time from research to market of sustainable renovation solutions – in particular, those innovations being created and developed in EU-funded projects in Horizon Europe Cluster 5 (and beyond, in the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, as well as other European, National and Regional R&I programmes).

3 TOWARDS SUPPORTING INNOVATION CLUSTERS NETWORKS

This section introduces to the B4P objectives and the NEB principles and shows that the elicitation process of an IC to become a B4PIC is developed in respect to and based on both (B4P and NEB) complementary frameworks. In other words, our approach is developed in a way to ensure its model is conceptually compliant to both B4P and NEB visions and related methodologies, and thus can be enriched and scaled up for further development by keeping its consistency and applicability.

3.1 B4P general and specific objectives

B4PICs respect the B4P vision described in the B4P Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (B4P SRIA 2022), they share and communicate to their members (most of) the B4P objectives. This refers to both 3 B4P general objectives and 7 B4P specific objectives.

Three B4P general objectives are as follows:

1. “Scientific”: to generate holistic innovation towards sustainability;
2. “Economic”: to revitalize the sector through decarbonization and sustainability transition;
3. “Societal”: to induce lasting behavioral change towards sustainable living.

They are concretized by seven B4P specific objectives:

- A. Develop holistic solutions in a systemic approach;
- B. Demonstrate overall performance in the life-cycle perspective;

- C. Demonstrate clean energy transition potential;
- D. Demonstrate sector decarbonization pathways;
- E. Demonstrate sustainable, circular business and value chain;
- F. Demonstrate affordability and cost-effectiveness;
- G. Demonstrate no trade-offs on economy, comfort, health, functions, cultural heritage.

3.2 NEB core values and working principles

By engaging to foster EU-scale, multidisciplinary and sustainable innovation in the Built Environment, B4PICs will be particularly encouraged to better account for the NEB core value and working principles described by (NEB Compass 2022) enabling the green transition of our societies and economy.

There are three NEB core values:

- Aesthetics (beautiful): emphasizing the importance of aesthetics and creativity in enhancing the quality of life and well-being of individuals and communities;
- Sustainability (sustainable): encouraging the use of sustainable materials, energy-efficient design, and circular economy principles in architecture, urban planning, and design;
- Inclusivity (together): ensuring that the built environment is accessible and inclusive for all members of society, regardless of age, ability, or background.

The ways of operating and working to address these three core values are described by three NEB working principles:

- Participatory process; inclusion of all groups of the civil society in the decision-making processes;
- Multi-level engagement: fostering exchange between peers (horizontal exchange) and between groups in different scales (vertical exchange);
- Transdisciplinary approach: collaboration between different fields of knowledge.

These working principles aim at involving all members of society in an open and equal manner. They promote a fair transformational outcome which is not only accepted, but also beneficial for everyone and mindful of the systemic and close relationships between complex social, environmental and structural factors. Moreover, they also yield knowledge and insights which can be scaled up and transferred to other outcomes or fields of knowledge.

3.3 B4P/NEB foundations of the IC-to-B4PIC elicitation process

Our approach for the elicitation process of an IC to become a B4PIC is designed to be conceptually compliant to both B4P and NEB frameworks.

First, it is important to underline that despite different origins, the B4P general objectives and the NEB core values are conceptually based on the same

principles towards sustainability, aesthetics and inclusion from scientific, economic and societal points of view. Moreover, there is a strong interdependence between the seven specific B4P objectives and the NEB core values and working principles. These interdependencies are concretized by B4P outcomes related to seven B4P specific objectives, which are defined in the B4P Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda.

Indeed, in the context of our approach, this comparative analysis is developed for all B4P specific objectives and all NEB core values and working principles.

This allows three conclusions:

- any IC sharing B4P general and specific objectives and aiming at (some of) them is potentially NEB-compliant;
- the maturity level of a B4PIC can be defined and evaluated on the basis of the B4PIC success factors, by introducing maturity levels for each success factor;
- the B4PIC maturity framework is thus coherent with the B4P and NEB frameworks.

Moreover, since the B4PIC maturity framework is based on the B4P and NEB core principles, it remains conceptually coherent if additional new elements of the B4P and/or NEB frameworks are introduced (e.g. following updating of the B4P Research and Innovation Agenda and/or further development of the NEB Compass).

4 B4PIC MATURITY FRAMEWORK

The B4PIC maturity framework is an evaluation framework to assess the maturity of B4PICs according to six success factors (introduced in Section 2.3) for the deployment and outreach of clusters.

4.1 Maturity levels of success factors

For each success factor (SF), three levels (low, medium, high) of its maturity are identified.

For SF1, “whole value chain”, they are described by the following levels:

- Level 1 (low) of SF1 maturity is held by those ICs that gather stakeholders with same professions (e.g. only academia, only industrials);
- Level 2 (medium) of SF1 maturity relates to those IC who gather stakeholders with a few distinct profiles, but still do not address the whole value chain;
- Level 3 (high) of SF1 maturity is reached by those ICs which integrate stakeholders from various domains: research, industry, public authorities, citizen associations (including NGOs).

The maturity levels for SF2, “Multi-objectives” are defined by:

- Level 1 (low) of SF2 maturity when an IC is focused on only one type of objectives (e.g. sustainability, decarbonization, energy efficiency);

- Level 2 (medium) of SF2 maturity corresponds to the case when an IC simultaneously addresses different groups of objectives (e.g. circularity and integrating cultural values into design);
- Level 3 (high) of SF2 maturity is reached by those ICs which not only address the 7 B4P specific objectives and NEB core values working principles, but also actively promote some or all of them. This can be done, for example, by nominating a NEB advisor from members of the cluster who would disseminate the NEB vision and facilitate the adoption of its principles, together with the B4P objectives.

As for SF3, “Cross-sectoral”, maturity levels are concerned, they are as follows:

- Level 1 (low) of SF3 maturity is a basic level of cross-sectoral collaboration when an IC is focused on one sector (it would however typically address multiple applications);
- Level 2 (medium) of SF3 maturity refers to the case when an IC focuses on one sector, but clusters with another IC from a different sector;
- Level 3 (high) of SF3 maturity is the next stage of cross-sectoral collaboration: while an IC is still mainly focused on one sector, it has already actively engaged in clustering and joint road mapping with several clusters from different sectors (whose members might be trans-disciplinary).

The SF4, “Locally anchored with National and European outreach” defines the level of vertical integration of an IC into local / regional / national / European networks with three maturity levels:

- Level 1 (low) of SF4 maturity is characteristic for a local/regional IC;
- Level 2 (medium) of SF4 maturity corresponds to the case when a local/ regional IC is connected to one or a few other local/regional ICs from the same or a different country (this might involve joint activities, exchanges between members, etc.);
- Level 3 (high) of SF4 maturity is achieved by an IC, which is vertically integrated in the national construction technology platform and/or other ecosystems and networks: e.g. ECTP/METABUILDING Built Environment ecosystem, B4P network.

SF5 “Cross-border” maturity levels reflect the level of interconnections of an IC with clusters from other regions or Member States. The corresponding SF5 maturity levels are identified as follows:

- Level 1 (low) of SF5 maturity corresponds to an IC, which has no cross-border interactions;
- Level 2 (medium) of SF5 maturity is reached by an IC with a few cross-border contacts, which is actively promoting interregional activities and programmes to its members;
- Level 3 (high) of SF5 maturity is a next step, when an IC has implemented at least one strategic relationship with a cluster from another country

(for example within an Euroregion) and engages in joint road mapping in line with requirements for this region.

The maturity levels of SF6 “Access to testbeds and demonstration spaces” define how an IC integrates and/or connects to test beds, pilot buildings, living labs or other facilities to demonstrate innovations and facilitate market uptake. They are:

- Level 1 (low) of SF6 maturity corresponds to the case when an IC has no connection to testbeds and demonstration spaces;
- Level 2 (medium) of SF6 maturity defines ICs that have contacts with local/ regional testbeds and demonstration spaces to facilitate for its members the demonstration and market uptake of their innovations;
- Level 3 (high) of SF6 maturity is reached when an IC is actively seeking testing opportunities for its members using the services of Open Innovation Testbeds like METABUILDING LABS, iClimabuilt, MEZeroE providing co-development and testing opportunities with real users (LivingLabs).

4.2 Maturity levels of B4PICs

Based on the B4PIC maturity framework, the proposed approach identifies three levels of B4P Innovation Clusters, according to their maturity.

- Prospective B4PIC (candidate) is an IC which expressed interest in and is exploring the possibility of becoming a B4PIC, in synergy with the B4P Partnership. This IC engages to aim at all B4PIC success factors (but this does not imply the obligation to have achieved all of them). Moreover, a Prospective B4PIC should have the maturity of all six success factors at least at level 1;
- Emerging B4PIC is a B4PIC that has developed and signed their B4PIC Charter on the basis of a commitment to progress towards required maturity (but is not meeting these minimum requirements yet). The timeline to reach the desired maturity levels for each success factor are specified in their B4PIC Charter (e.g. 12 months to reach medium maturity level for SF3, 24 months to reach high maturity level for SF6, etc.);
- Established B4PIC is an Emerging B4PIC that reaches the highest maturity level (level 3) for at least 3 of 6 success factors, from which 2 success factors are mandatory. The mandatory success factors are SF1 “Whole value chain” and SF2 “Multi-objectives”; the third success factor with highest level of maturity can be defined by each B4PIC according to their profiles and development targets. Analogically to Emerging B4PICs, the timeline to achieve the aimed maturity level for Established B4PICs is also specifically set for each success factor in the signed B4PIC Charter.

In order to become an Established B4PIC, a Prospective B4PIC is thus requested to mature along the six success factors of the B4PIC maturity framework.

5 CLUSTERS' MATURITY PROCESS

The journey of an IC to become a B4PIC and be integrated into the B4PIC network is illustrated at Figure 2.

Figure 2. IC-to-B4PIC cluster journey

Practically, this process can be summarized as follows.

First, an IC self-evaluates its current maturity for each success factor according to the defined B4PIC maturity framework.

Additionally, it sets some maturity improvement targets. It needs to define which success factors and maturity levels will be reached at the end of the transformation process.

The IC should also present an envisaged brief implementation plan explaining the steps to reach this goal. The implementation plan should include a timeline to achieve the defined maturity level for the chosen success factors. It is anticipated that at least 3 among the 6 success factors should reach the highest level of maturity the B4PIC implementation plan.

Time	Whole value chain	Multi-objectives	Cross-sectoral	Locally anchored with national and European outreach	Cross-border	Access to testbeds and demonstration spaces
t0 (signing the Charter)	M1.1 IC gathers stakeholders with same professions (e.g., only academia, only industrials, ...)	M2.1 IC is focused on one type of objectives (e.g., sustainability, decarbonization applications, ...)	M3.1 IC is focused on one sector (but addressing multiple applications)	M4.1 IC is local/regional	M5.1 IC has no cross-border interactions	M6.1 IC has no connection to testbeds and demonstration spaces
t0+6	M1.1	M2.2 IC addresses different groups of objectives (e.g., circularity and integrating cultural values into design, ...)	M3.2 IC is focused on one sector but clusters with one IC from a different sector	M4.1	M5.1	M6.1

Figure 3. Example (extract) of the implementation plan for the maturity of an B4PIC

An example of such an implementation plan (extract) is shown at Figure 3. At that stage, the main

challenges identified so far along this maturity process can be summarised as follows:

- Ensure the completeness of the value-chain covered by the B4PIC, considering the mission and ambition of the innovation ecosystem, as well as the appropriate interactions between actors of the innovation value chain and across sectors and disciplines at regional/local, national and (potentially) EU level;
- Provide cluster members with the effective enabling conditions for innovation, in particular for SMEs. Such conditions should include the economic, environmental and social assessment of innovations in the construction and renovation field by leveraging on SMEs' innovative products and systems; and the direct engagement of users/citizens in development;
- As per the B4PIC network itself and in a longer-term perspective, provide the necessary basis (methodologies and supporting tools) for the replication of the concepts and procedures to develop such network, ensuring its long-term sustainability even beyond the termination of the European B4P Partnership.

6 FIRST PROSPECTIVE B4PICS

The first front-runner clusters, Build:INN⁶ (previously known as Eraikune), and Odéys⁷, who are partners of the NEBULA project too, have become Emerging B4PICs and joined the B4PIC network after signing their B4PIC Charter in September 2023.

At the moment of the signature of the B4PIC Charter, both clusters already achieved the highest maturity level for two of the B4PIC success factors: SF1: Whole value chain and SF3: Cross-sectoral. Moreover, the Build:INN cluster also had the highest maturity level on SF4: Locally anchored with national and European clusters, whilst the Odéys cluster was characterised by a medium maturity of this success factor. For other three success factors – SF2: Multi-objectives, SF5: Cross-border, SF6: Access to testbeds and demonstration spaces – both Build:INN and Odéys had the medium level of maturity at the moment of the signature of their B4PIC Charters.

According to their implementation plan defined in their respective B4PIC Charters, both clusters plan to increase their maturity related to SF2, SF4, SF5 and SF6 and thus achieve the highest maturity level for all the six success factors in 24 months from the moment of the Charter signature: i.e., by September 2025.

⁶ [Clúster de construcción del País Vasco | Build:INN \(buildinn.eu\)](https://buildinn.eu)

⁷ [Cluster Odéys | Cluster construction et aménagements durables \(odeys.fr\)](https://odeys.fr)

The first open call for EoI for ICs to become B4PICs and join the B4PIC network was launched in autumn 2023 till the end of 2023.

Figure 4. Emerging and Prospective B4PICs (April 2024)

It resulted in 54 applications of EoI from stakeholders in Europe, from which 26 ICs were short-listed and invited to complete the Self-Assessment Tool (SAT), an online questionnaire to self-evaluate their maturity level. This led to 16 Prospective B4PICs from 10 European countries, who have been selected to sign the B4PIC Charter by end of NEBULA (March 2025). The current status of Prospective and Emerging B4PICs is shown in Figure 4.

As it can be seen on the map, some Member States are over-represented (e.g. Spain, Italy, France) while other Member States are not covered yet. Future EoI or activities carried out to expand the B4PIC network should target those countries in priority, to ensure that EU27 is covered as best as possible. Such expansion is foreseen in the framework of the EU-funded project STAR*track (GA N° 101147509).

7 CONCLUSION

The B4P Partnership is a policy cross-cutting initiative, addressing buildings climate-neutrality as well as sustainability as a whole: reducing resource intensity and increasing recyclability, taking into consideration other policies relevant to buildings, including the need to preserve our European Cultural Heritage. It gathers innovation stakeholders across the whole value chain for a cleaner, safer, inclusive, decarbonised and sustainable Built Environment. These stakeholders produce, integrate and deliver people-centric holistic innovation, along with high quality architecture.

Innovation Clusters are key actors in the innovation landscape as they foster cooperation in the Construction value chain. Thanks to the support of the NEBULA project, a comprehensive methodology has been developed to formalise the concept of B4PIC and nurture a network of such B4PICs all

over Europe, leveraging on the B4P objectives and NEB values to enhance the user-centric dimension of innovation.

A first wave of B4PICs has been consolidated in the first half of 2024, and it is anticipated that new B4PICs will continuously integrate the B4PIC network. Beyond supporting the B4PICs with tools and services, the network also encourages knowledge sharing with regard to innovative assets, experiences and good practices between the member clusters. The operational performance of the network will be carefully evaluated and improved in the coming months and years. As such, the anticipated future developments and prospective activities can be summarised as follows:

- re-enforcing the enabling conditions (supported by providing tools and training) for B4PICs and their members for increased development and market transfer of innovation for the Built Environment;
- accelerating the demonstration of holistic and inclusive solutions with high market potential through tailored support mechanisms, leveraging on demonstration sites, open innovation test-beds, and living labs;
- facilitating access to funding for demonstration, scale-up and implementation of sustainable innovation by local/regional construction value chains.

The overarching aim for next steps is to pave the way for replication, wide-spread use of the supporting tools and services, and continuous expansion of the B4PICs network based on a replication plan with a long-term vision and business model – potentially covering the EU27 by 2028 (and the end of the Horizon Europe Framework Programme proposed in 2018).

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9 REFERENCES

The European Green Deal. 2019, available at [The European Green Deal - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-operations/infographic-1163236663469-10162023-1.pdf), last accessed 04.04.2024

⁸ <https://built4people.eu/nebula/>

- Fit for 55 Package. 2023, available at [Fit for 55 - The EU's plan for a green transition - Consilium \(europa.eu\)](#), last accessed 04.04.2024
- Kasi, A.S. Hannus M. Zarli A. Bourdeau M. 2015. Towards strategic actions for ICT R&D in construction. *eWork and eBusiness in Architecture, Engineering and Construction*: 31-39
- New European Bauhaus. 2021, available at [New European Bauhaus: beautiful, sustainable, together. - European Union \(europa.eu\)](#), last accessed 04.04.2024
- Yfanti S. Temple B. Sakkas N. 2017. Innovation and Clustering: Lessons from the Construction sector and Critical Success Factors for adoption and implementation. Lost cause or lacuna? *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, vol. 6, issue 61, February 2017. ISSN: 2251-8843
- Meng, H. 2005. Innovation cluster as the national competitiveness tool in the innovation driven economy. *International Journal of Foresight and Innovation Policy*, 2(1), 2005: 104-110.
- Press, K. 2006. A Life Cycle for Clusters? Heidelberg, Germany: *Physica-Verlag*: 264.
- Engel, Jerome S. 2022. Global Clusters of Innovation: lessons from Silicon Valley, California Management Review, winter 2015, Vol. 57 Issue 2, pp. 36-65 / Engel, Jerome S, *Clusters of Innovation in the Age of Disruption*, Edward Elgar Publishing, ISBN: 978 1 80088 515 8, 7 July 2022.
- Communication from the Commission Framework for State aid for research and development and innovation 2022/C 414/01, *Official Journal of the European Union*, 28.10.2022, available at [eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52022XC1028\(03\)](#), last accessed 31.03.2024
- Lau Insider. 2024, available at [innovation clusters Definition | Law Insider](#), last accessed 04.04.2024
- OISPG. 2015. Open Innovation Strategy and Policy Group from the EC (supported by DG Connect)., available at <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/open-innovation-publications>, last accessed 04.06.2024
- B4P Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda. 2022, available online at [Built4People-Partnership-SRIA-March-2022.pdf](#), last accessed 04.04.2024
- NEB Compass. 2022, available at [405245f4-6859-4090-b145-1db88f91596d_en \(europa.eu\)](#), last accessed 04.04.2024
- Horizon Europe Framework Programme. 2018, available online at https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en, last accessed 04.04.2024